

ENACT – A Framework for Adaptive Scheduling and Deployments of Data Intensive Workloads on Energy Efficient Edge to Cloud Continuum (pre-print)

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Abstract— In the last couple of decades, enterprises have relished and leveraged the capacity, performance, scalability, and quality of cloud computing services. However, a few years ago, the edge computing concept enabled data processing and application execution near compute and data resources, aiming to reduce latency and promote higher security and sovereignty regarding data transfers. The simultaneous use of these two service models by enterprises has lately resulted in the concept of edge-to-cloud continuum, which combines edge and cloud technologies and promotes standards and algorithms for resource orchestration, data management, and the deployment of solutions across the connected edge and cloud resources. Taking a step further in this direction, this paper introduces a framework to realise the Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC). The framework leverages AI techniques to address the needs for optimal (edge and cloud) resource management and dynamic scaling, elasticity, and portability of hyper-distributed data-intensive applications. The proposed ENACT framework enables the automated management of distributed (edge and cloud) resources and the development of hyper-distributed applications that can take advantage of distributed deployment and execution opportunities to optimize their behaviors in terms of execution time, resource utilisation and energy efficiency.

Keywords—compute continuum, edge, cloud, orchestration

I. INTRODUCTION

The European industrial technology roadmap for the next generation cloud-edge offering [1] highlights the emergence of a new generation of flagship hyperconnected and hyper-distributed service initiatives such as DestinE [2], the

Metaverse/W3C Web3¹, Holographic-type Telepresence [3], Autonomous Hyperconnected Urban Mobility [4] etc. All those applications are content intensive and will impact how we experience our Digital Life, how and where we will consume and use 2D/3D content of different kinds (entertainment, cultural, heritage, creative) as well as 3D models/Digital Twin for different purposes (autonomous green mobility, smart tourism, entertainment). As highlighted in EBDVF 2022 Congress, Metaverse and Web 3.0 [5] have grown in popularity as "the successor to the mobile Internet". The Web 3.0 is a paradigm shift of the Internet towards user-centric decentralization. The primary principles of Web 3.0 will be especially realized in the Metaverse, which is the next stage in the development of the Internet. The Metaverse is expected to be a seamless and interoperable integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven virtual worlds populated by user generated contents (UGCs), and accessible through virtual/augmented reality (VR/AR) technologies. The metaverse, only, could contribute €2.8 trillion to the global GDP. In Europe, an expansion of the virtual world could mean a contribution of 1.7 per cent – or €417 billion – to the continent's economy in 10 years. As already highlighted by the 2022 NEM research challenges[6], all these new forms of exploiting and consuming content will demand challenging physical-virtual world synchronization for 3D world building, high resolution streaming of 3D objects, real-time execution of the perception-actuation loop on the Internet of Things (IoT), with a dedicated and high-performance demand for edge operations.

¹ <https://www.w3.org/2007/Talks/0123-sb-W3CEmergingTech/>

The cloud-edge continuum has so far developed many forms of flexibility and adaptation, yet it lacks disruptive technologies to deal effectively with the new forms in which content (user generated and-or professionally produced) will be distributed and consumed across extended reality, mobile, fixed or virtual world platforms. In this respect, a specific demand exists to build a computing continuum with cognitive Web3 capabilities that can effectively (climate neutrality, performance, user experience) enact and seamlessly manage (with European values) this explosion of locally generated content (2D/3D video, images, visualizations, point clouds) for next generation hyper-distributed services.

The proposed ENACT framework raises from current CEI² architectures and frameworks to disruptively addresses precisely this need for efficient and intelligent content & data processing using all suitable resources available in the edge-cloud continuum. Such need arises from the fact that not all applications and services are suited for either pure edge or pure cloud computing. Instead, many modern applications require a combination of both edge and cloud computing to achieve the desired level of performance, scalability, and cost effectiveness. For example, the use of high-definition cameras for broadcasting live events is not only adding to the complexity of techniques and technologies required for handling large volumes of data; but also, to the complexity of finding and managing infrastructure across different venues that can support extraction of real-time insights and decision-making. To address such needs, ENACT offers breakthrough techniques and disruptive technology solutions to support dynamic discovering and utilising of available infrastructure (such as edge and cloud nodes) and the design and development of distributed applications and systems that can take advantage of the different types of compute and storage resources available in the compute continuum.

Recently, there have been significant developments in ad-hoc networking techniques and as a result various mature approaches for edge-cloud and fog computing currently exist [7]. A key objective of such approaches is to enable meshed networking at a high pace and frequency to support the dynamic scaling of applications across different nodes. This meshed networking has eliminated the concept of fixed infrastructures and has led to devices sharing status information anywhere in the computing environment, allowing the applications to make critical decisions concerning resource utilisation. However, where on one hand, automated deployment and run-time management of distributed applications in cloud environments is relatively well studied with several mature solutions. On the other hand, managing such applications and tasks in the cloud-to-edge continuum is far from trivial, with no robust, production-level solutions currently available. In this direction, EU Data Strategy [8] sets the cloud-to-edge continuum paradigm as a strategic technology towards European leadership in the digital space.

With this background, the ENACT framework focuses on realising a Cognitive Compute Continuum that can support handling/processing of big data from multiple sources, getting real-time insight from large volumes of data, providing

personalized experience to the target users based on the real-time insight, automation of routine tasks for greater efficiency of the overall system, and performing predictive maintenance of the resources to reduce downtime or unexpected issues. ENACT introduces tools to connect and discover distributed resources, devices and services across the compute continuum, characterize and model them; to support complex application deployment and execution needs; (b) an AI-powered orchestrator, capable of deploying and managing applications across distributed (edge and cloud) nodes in an optimal way to support the energy efficiency and adaptations in distributed applications; and (c) an application development toolkit for developing or adapting complex applications; making them distributed, robust and adaptive in order to optimize their performance and take advantage of the resources in the CCC.

Following the Introduction, the remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Chapter II presents a brief overview of current state of the in cloud-edge continuums and related technologies, Chapter III introduces the ENACT concept, architecture and technologies, Chapter IV summarize to possible impact of ENACT realization and application and the Conclusions are drawn in the last chapter.

II. RELATED WORK

The Edge-Cloud Compute Continuum seamlessly integrates not only edge and cloud (hardware and software) resources, such as devices, servers and gateways, but also sophisticated mechanisms for orchestration, discovery, modelling, scheduling of distributed resources, programming models, portable services and applications, secure communication and distributed data storage. In this respect, background on some of the key technological areas related to Edge-Cloud Compute Continuum is presented in this section:

A. *Cloud-Edge Orchestration and Scheduling for efficient management of hyper-distributed applications in the CCC*

The major research challenges regarding orchestration in cloud-to-edge continuums are resource visibility [9] dynamic resource allocation [10] (e.g. due to resource uncertainty, energy constraints and dynamic dependencies), dynamic management of application elasticity and dynamic workload scheduling. In recent years, several cloud orchestration solutions have gained huge popularity, such as Kubernetes³, Cloudify⁴ and Docker Swarm⁵. Major cloud providers also offer tools for orchestration, such as AWS CloudFormation⁶ and Google's Deployment Manager⁷. Similarly, the connections and orchestrations considering edge resources are enabled by open-source KubeEdge [11]. However, the current solutions struggle to manage the dynamism (at application and infrastructure) at edge and fog computing environments, as they are primarily inspired by the reliability inherent in the cloud environments. In this direction, MiCADO [12] recently introduced an orchestrator towards cloud-to-edge continuum however it is focused more on the delivery of an operational solution and not on the improvement of the orchestrator's intelligence in dealing with complex and dynamic orchestration needs of applications. Distributed orchestration

² <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

³ <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁴ <https://docs.cloudify.co/latest/>

⁵ <https://docs.docker.com/engine/swarm/>

⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudformation/>

⁷ <https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace/product/google-cloud-platform/cloud-deployment-manager?pli=1>

approaches to guarantee QoS across Cloud–Edge continuum based on Kubernetes have been introduced in [13]. SmartORC [14] also uses a kind of optimization algorithms and matchmaking related to QoS to support orchestration. Moreover, recently the EC funded knowlEdge project [15] introduced a cloud-edge continuum that orchestrates AI models execution. However, the techniques developed in knowledge are only focused on the distributed execution of AI models and do not take into account the runtime deployment distribution and elasticity aspects that can arise in dynamic enterprise applications.

Based on recent research outcomes, the underlying intelligence in an orchestrator, tuned for edge and cloud resource management, can be based on approaches such as search-based algorithms, mathematical programming algorithms and game-theoretical or deep learning algorithms e.g. AI4DL [16] shows how to manage distributed resources by analyzing deep learning workloads. Similarly, Theta-Scan leverages behavior analysis to auto-scale containers in the cloud. RL also introduced [17] a method for cloud-edge-fog orchestration and scheduling. However, reinforcement learning on its own requires a lot of learning/training data, which can be difficult to acquire for dynamic applications with unique deployment and execution characteristics.

B. Discovery and modelling of distributed services and resources in the computing continuum

Current distributed cognitive computing applications represent several challenges for the compute continuum owing to their complex nature and specific constraints covering aspects such as resources, workloads, performance, and application behaviour. Representation of different entities in the Cloud to Edge compute continuum can be done through the use of service discovery, resource discovery, and device discovery techniques. There exist many methods of resource discovery [18] including centralized and distributed architectures such as Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) based service discovery, edge-centric distributed discovery, semantic-based discovery, search engine resource discovery, and utilisation of Object Name Service (ONS) and Domain Name Service (DNS). Distributed and Peer-to-Peer (P2P) discovery services utilise Distributed Hash Table (DHT) as a core technique as it can support multi-range queries, and communications between different IoT artefacts [19]. The unique characteristics of edge environments such as limited resources and heterogeneity pose additional challenges on resource discovery [20]. Moreover, the elastic nature of modern distributed applications requires enhanced visibility of the available resources (in the compute continuum) and the connectivity between them in order to support applications.

C. Application Programming Models and portable services to support hyper-distributed applications

Distributed applications are increasingly relying on computing and storage resources available in the edge and fog clusters to address their needs for efficient data processing and decision making. The use of microservice-based architectures

is common in the design of distributed applications where microservices can perform common tasks such as service discovery, load balancing, fault tolerance, monitoring, security. However, implementing these tasks in each microservice can be tedious, error-prone and inconsistent. Several frameworks for supporting the development or distributed applications such as Dapr⁸ provide a portable runtime for building resilient and stateful microservices using any language and framework. Similarly, Envoy [21] is an edge and service proxy that can be deployed as a sidecar to enable dynamic service discovery and load balancing. Istio service mesh can enhance the security, reliability and observability of distributed applications by providing a uniform way to connect, manage and monitor microservices. Moreover, in the EC funded ECO2Cloud project [32] investigated runtime application runtime adaptation strategies for a given context, that could allow the improvements in application execution behaviours based on the analysis of trade-off between QoS and CO₂ emission reduction. However, the effectiveness of such strategies for applications running on the edge is not evident since the adaptation strategies were evaluated only for HPC applications. Furthermore, approaches like COMP Superscalar [22] provide a programming model that aims to ease the development of parallel applications to run atop distributed infrastructures. Recently a middleware to enable applications' portability in heterogeneous clouds was introduced [23] but it is currently not investigated for edge/fog deployment of applications.

D. Zero-touch Provisioning (ZTP) to automate configuration of devices across CCC and Next Generation Software Defined Networking for automated control of CCC communication

Low-touch provisioning (LTP) and zero-touch provisioning (ZTP) [24] are introduced to simplify and automate the onboarding of new devices to be connected in a network or in a cloud service [25]. In this direction, Cisco has introduced its Firepower⁹ system that utilizes LTP for connection with Cisco Defence Orchestrator. Their approach is based on serial/ID number provisioning and confirmation by remote branch administrator. Similarly, FortiGate¹⁰ (ZTP) & (LTP) services are provided by using a USB drive containing the configuration file (LTP method) or by using FortiDeploy (ZTP method), a cloud based approval capitalizing on key-type registration for approval. Arista ZTP¹¹ is also introducing an approach related to ZTP for scalable clouds' deployment by using a configuration file and populating its contents into a system database. An approach related to NTP/ZTP for IoT devices is provided by Digi Remote Manager¹² that offers a cloud-based service that automates the configuration process for devices. Beyond ZTP another technology, the Software Defined Networking has revolutionized how networks are structured and operated. SDN enables simpler and more reliable control mechanisms through well-defined interfaces. The first generation of SDN technology was characterized by a fixed set of features limiting capabilities of the platform to those offered by the data plane devices [26]. The next generation of SDN embraces Whitebox hardware and open interfaces enabling

⁸ <https://dapr.io/>

⁹ https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/td/docs/security/firepower/quick_start/fp1010/firepower-1010-gsg/m_1010-ltp.html

¹⁰ <https://docs.fortinet.com/document/fortigate/6.2.13/cookbook/135501/zero-touch-provisioning>

¹¹ <https://www.arista.com/en/solutions/zero-touch-provisioning>

¹² <https://www.digi.com/products/iot-software-services/digi-remote-manager>

administrators to enforce custom behaviour to data plane devices and produce finer packet level measurements

E. Distributed Data and Object Data Sharing

Federated cloud environments such as GAIA-X¹³ and initiatives like IDSA¹⁴ and FIWARE¹⁵ deliver infrastructure, reference architectures and formal standards to enable secure and trustworthy data-sharing[27][28]. Based on popular standards, secure and trustworthy data sharing can be supported by data connectors and APIs (Open API standards), with security delegated in third-party components. Current approaches are based on containers and virtualization concepts, and they are mainly focused on data sharing. However, in the distributed application the need for sharing of data (as chunks and streams) is often complemented by the need for sharing data objects[29]. Regarding the objects sharing and distributed management, there are some distributed storages such as Amazon S3¹⁶ and BSC dataClay [30], a distributed data store that enables applications to store and access objects in the same format they have in memory, however they are not designed to support the notion of trusted shared dataspace and are bounded by proprietary software and platforms.

The following table summarizes current solutions per technological area and ENACT advancements.

Technological Area	Current Solutions Summary	ENACT Advancements
Cloud-Edge Orchestration and Scheduling	Mainly consider cloud or edge orchestration and not a full continuum. The orchestration solutions are based on game theory, deep learning and search based algorithms	Innovative AI Orchestrator based on combination of GNNs and Reinforcement Learning for optimal orchestration
Discovery and modelling of distributed services	Current solutions are quite complex and are covering aspects such as resources, workloads, performance, and application behaviour without user friendly and interpretable considerations.	A visual dynamic graph modelling tool will be developed to support the analysis, modelling and discovery of distributed resources and their relationships in the compute continuum.
Application Programming Models & Apps	Portable runtime and microservices logic is available in current sota but not connected with edge/fog approaches	Application Programming Model to enable the development of platform agnostic hyper-distributed applications based on the code-based portable microservice principles
Zero-touch Provisioning & SDN	ZTP services are mainly available at network level without considering further aspects/components in a CCC. SDN technology is characterised by a fixed set of features limiting capabilities of the platform	ZTP service for dynamically connecting and utilizing cloud or on edge devices Next-generation SDN will enable administrators to enforce custom behavior to data plane devices and produce finer packet level measurements

Technological Area	Current Solutions Summary	ENACT Advancements
Distributed Data and Object Data Sharing	Data Space concepts and components available based on IDSA and Gaia-X paradigm Distributed data storages for objects available	ENACT will combine data spaces concepts with distributed objects stores to provide sovereign data and object access across CCC

III. ENACT COGNITIVE COMPUTING CONTINUUM

ENACT introduces a concept for a cognitive compute continuum, that investigates various areas that are discussed in the previous chapter and proposes breakthrough ideas to extend the state of art in these areas.

A. ENACT Concept

ENACT addresses the needs for hyper-distributed computing and real-time processing of large amounts of data, taking advantage of the diverse data handling, computing and storage facilities across the compute continuum. The availability of high-performance edge devices, in addition to the Cloud and HPC facilities, open new opportunities for the distribution and optimal execution of data intensive applications. By developing ad-hoc networking, graph-based modelling, dynamic discovery and adaptive orchestration techniques, ENACT aims to realize a Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC), where distributed, opportunistic, collaborative, heterogeneous and adaptive applications can make effective use of the available edge-to-cloud resources and optimize their behaviour in terms of performance, energy efficiency and resilience. Towards this aim, ENACT introduces techniques and tools for dynamic networking of edge-cloud resources (through ZTP & programmable network fabric), real-time modelling of distributed edge-cloud resources and visibility of their connections (through dynamic graph models), intelligent orchestration and dynamic deployments of applications (through graph neural networks) and adaptation in application execution behaviours (through application programming model and runtime adaptation techniques).

Through the aforementioned techniques and tools, ENACT aims to support the deployment and execution requirements of hyper-distributed applications that can take advantage of the resources, devices and services exposed in centralized, distributed or hybrid Cluster Models within the CCC. Moreover, the proposed ENACT solutions are designed to enable the elasticity, scalability and dynamism in intelligent and autonomous applications by providing them necessary visibility of available (compute and storage) resources together with the decision making (or adaptation) capability to help them optimize their execution behavior across different layers of the compute continuum at the Cloud, Edge and Far-Edge levels. The conceptual approach underpinning the ENACT solutions is illustrated in Fig 1.

¹³ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

¹⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.fiware.org/>

¹⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

Fig. 1 ENACT High-level Concept

B. ENACT Approach

A key factor in the Cognitive Computing Continuum is the availability of self-adaptive applications and systems that can take advantage of the dynamic and distributed (deployment and execution) opportunities that can be found from suitable resources to relevant cloud clusters. The use of fixed deployment configurations (at application level) or heuristic orchestration rules (or scheduler level) based on simple criteria (such as available capacity) fall short of taking full advantage of the CCC. Thus, ENACT proposes dynamic graph-based edge-to-cloud resource modelling to support real-time visibility, automatic discovery, continuous self-adaptation and predictive management of federated edge and cloud cluster resources based on cluster and telemetry data. The dynamic graph models will support optimal deployment of distributed applications and runtime adaptations in application deployments based on real-time availability of suitable resources as well as predictions on the availability and behaviours of resources (e.g. in terms of latency, power, energy consumption etc).

To advantage of the real-time availability of data concerning distributed edge and cloud resources, together with their interconnections and dependencies, ENACT proposes a beyond state-of-the-art AI (Graph Neural Networks and Reinforcement Learning) powered edge-to-cloud scheduler that uses (a) real-time information from edge-cloud resource (or CCC dynamic graph models populated by telemetry data), and (b) parameterized information from edge-cloud systems (such as security policies, access controls or localized optimization policies) to provision, allocate, scale, downgrade, rebalance the resources and workloads in a bid to support the optimization at both the application as well as the underlying infrastructure levels.

Based on the GNN and RL algorithms/models, the ENACT AI-enabled scheduler will learn from deployment decisions, application execution behaviours, infrastructure performance and other optimization criteria (e.g. power usage, energy efficiency, communication bandwidth etc.) to improve its performance or decision making over time and overcome threats, such as performance degradation of computing nodes, device churn, communication problems, adherence of new devices (business partners) or abnormal situations that require a self-adjustment of certain networking devices or IT systems.

Fig. 2 ENACT Cognitive Orchestrator

In addition to the dynamic graph models, AI scheduler and ZTP technologies for CCC, the ENACT Application Programming Model (APM) is also proposed. The APM is primarily aimed at supporting the development of dynamic and adaptive applications that can take full advantage of the distributed resources and services in the CCC. The CCC provides, under non-intrusive sidecar libraries, mechanisms to secure, self-register, model, identify, synchronize, communicate, continuous monitoring and autonomously operate hyper-distributed applications. Through novel architecture and technological support, APM will support specifications of applications optimized for cloud, edge and far-edge deployment.

C. ENACT Architecture

The proposed architecture of the overall ENACT solution is illustrated in Fig 3. It encompasses several modules and cutting-edge components that are organized in five main layers:

- ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer
- ENACT Data Layer
- ENACT Application Development Layer
- ENACT Continuum Vertical Services Layer
- ENACT Physical Layer

All the layers and their underlying components will be distributed for deployment across all the different levels in the compute continuum, such as Cloud, Fog and Edge.

ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer is responsible for AI services of the project especially optimizing the provisioning and management of resources, devices and services. This layer includes the ENACT Modelling sub-layer that will enable the dynamic graph-based modelling of edge-to-cloud nodes and their representation as GNNs. The CCC Graph Modeler will provide a studio environment and enable the self-discovery and dynamic updates of CCC Graph Models through its integration with a Telemetry Service responsible for gathering monitoring data from the distributed resources. The Telemetry Service will use a common data model to describe aspects like computational, memory and storage metrics. ENACT Data Space connectors will also support this service and data model, as the relevant data can also be made available in the ENACT Data Space. For network metrics, the NG-SDN architecture will ensure the availability of relevant data to the Telemetry Service. The CCC Graph Modeler Studio will provide a (network diagram

like) drag and drop functionality, allowing users to create graph models and link them with relevant data from the Telemetry Service.

Fig. 3 ENACT Architecture

ENACT Application Development Layer enables applications to take advantage of the diverse resources in the compute continuum, they must exhibit certain characteristics, such as dynamism, elasticity, parallelism or load balancing, self-optimization etc. To equip applications with such characteristics, ENACT incorporates in its architecture the ENACT Application Programming Model (APM) that enhances cloud and edge native applications with embedded AI and services such as communication, self-registration, identity management, state management, continuous monitoring. The Application Controller supports the autonomic self-optimization behavior and maintenance throughout the application lifetime. The Application Adaptation Engine is the core AI-adaptation mechanism that applies AI-based learning techniques to provide decision support to the Application Controller concerning the deployment and execution of ALPs. The Application Controller manages the overall application and communicates with ENACT Orchestrator(s) to manage the deployment and execution of the application. The Application Data Manager manages the storage and access to the data (e.g., in a shared data space) keeping consistency and synchronization of data along the CCC. To enable the development of ENACT applications and portable code-based microservices, ENACT includes a Software Development Kit (SDK) as an Eclipse SDK new plug-in.

ENACT Data Layer provides a Distributed Data and Object Space across the whole computing continuum. The enact project will promote cross-organization and platform data sharing by ENACT Secure Data Space Connector adhering to data sovereignty and governance principles as they are derived by leading initiatives like IDSA, GAIA-X, etc. Besides the connector, ENACT will incorporate a Distributed Data Manager component enabling the creation, management and validation of the entities and components in the compute continuum. ENACT will move a step further on data sharing and storage, by supporting an innovative sharing of objects between the applications in its Distributed Data and Objects Storage. As it would manage persistence of objects as they are handled by object-oriented programming languages, avoiding the mapping of data forms to objects of DBMS. Furthermore, the ENACT architecture through its component, Elasticity, Traffic and Load Manager will support the elasticity concept to provide the right level of service and authentication to real-time data streams as well as big data

workloads. Data Layer (in collaboration with Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer) will keep data close to the computation to reduce the latency and security concerns.

ENACT Continuum Vertical Services Layer capacitates the provisioning of various services that will act as enabler for the successful realization and delivery of the proposed continuum. This vertical layer includes components for secure communication, interoperable access to distributed environments and data, and dynamic connectivity. In particular, the project will encapsulate the ENACT Security module as an augmented decentralized telemetry service monitoring the continuum infrastructure based on NG-SDN architecture. Any detection of possible threats and security issues will be considered during orchestration and scheduling in ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer. ENACT Connectivity module will consider widely used and standardized data and communication protocols. Furthermore, it will enable the delivery of Zero Touch Provisioning (ZTP) service of the project for the dynamic and effortless access of new nodes in ENACT CCC. Interoperability services are also considered. Even though ENACT is not focused on development of data models and transformers, a module that will enable the modelling of data across ENACT CCC based on existing standards is included. This model is coupled with a pre-processing module and data transformation services that would be based on ETL(extract, transform, load) tools like Jolt to enable the handling of heterogeneous data formats. These modules and services mainly support ENACT Data Layer as vertical services.

ENACT Physical Layer is considered the lowest one in the project's architecture and contains the total of physical devices that will participate in ENACT CCC. Edge and Fog infrastructure from different deployment sites like IoT devices, sensors, cameras, mobile phones, networking & gateway devices alongside servers that will participate in piloting activities are included in this layer. Furthermore, High Performance Computing infrastructures that will be employed by the project will be considered in this layer as well (even though if they are considered as cloud infrastructure the actual machines are part of the physical world). This layer will be also responsible for defining the means of transmitting a stream of raw data/bits over a physical data link connecting network nodes based on hardware technologies with widely varying characteristics.

IV. PLANNED DEPLOYMENTS AND VALIDATIONS

The proposed ENACT solutions are currently planned for testing, monitoring, and validation across 3 different, yet complementary real-world scenarios that represent complex challenges in terms of large climate, social and geographical diversity of the infrastructure and service ecosystem. The test cases include distributed media and content management, management of heterogeneous media applications, and hyper-distributed data processing and orchestration of heterogeneous devices in the smart mobility domain. All of these scenarios will help test and validate the breakthrough approaches and technology solutions introduced in the earlier sections of this paper. Findings and validation results will be published in the subsequent publications – to be available at <https://enact-horizon.eu/>.

V. EXPECTED IMPACT OF ENACT IN EUROPEAN AND WORLDWIDE LANDSCAPE

The range of applications and workloads across different industries – each with unique cost, connectivity and performance, and security characteristics – will mandate a continuum of compute and analysis at every step of the topology, from the edge to the cloud. This continuum will require new approaches¹⁷ to orchestration, management, interoperability and security, and will result in a more agile data driven enterprise that is able to rapidly respond to the needs of stakeholders throughout the organization. The edge-to-cloud compute continuum is a foundational component of transformation into a data-driven enterprise. The edge computing market¹⁸ is expected to reach a potential value of \$155.90 billion by 2030, with a phenomenal CAGR of 38.9%. Moreover, according to [31], projected worldwide spending on edge computing in 2025, is growing at a CAGR of ~10%. The same study also reveals that innovative solutions like ENACT will provide a pathway both for networking service improvement (delivery optimization and catching); but also for improved quality of experience. Similar to ENACT, Meta has been working with Verizon¹⁹, a leading network provider, to create an cloud-edge computing and 5G environment for Metaverse universe development. ENACT will provide an open alternative to these American counterparts. Regarding, the ENACT verticals, they are heavily impacted by CCC technologies. Competitiveness and impact of European industry and edge will rely on smart orchestration of IoT edge-cloud data space continuum and on the ability of customize such continuum to the specific needs of each digital value chain application and service by means of smart (AI-powered) software-based management services – see European alliance²⁰ for industrial data, edge and cloud; precisely ENACT ambition.

A. Improved European leadership in the global data economy

The development of common standards, frameworks and infrastructures across Europe for Computing Continuum and Data Spaces technologies is a key element to create a more open and interoperable data ecosystem. ENACT will facilitate the development and deployment of Computing Continuum and Data Spaces technologies enabling the collaborations between different stakeholders, including industry, academia, and government in the European countries, supporting the creation of a more integrated data ecosystem. ENACT delivers an open source-based digital infrastructure to create data spaces following a trust centric approach that transforms the existing balance between cloud and edge workload by adopting intelligent decisions regarding data processing and leading to enhanced energy efficiency. By bringing computational and AI processing power closer to where data is generated, ENACT contributed to improving EU leadership in the global data economy, as it eliminates the dependency of EU data providers from cloud repositories, which in their vast majority are hosted by non-EU providers. Furthermore, ENACT leverages the principles of distributed learning and uses data for ML training that are collected by

edge nodes embedded in diverse environments, which in turn results in significant reduction of the training time, while, at the same time, leads to ML models that are more accurate, can be more easily generalized to be applied to other markets and paradigms. Finally, the adoption of the ENACT framework will nurture new business models and technical solutions that span through the continuum integrated in a dynamic and flexible ecosystem of resource providers

B. Maximised social and economic benefits from the wider and more effective use of data

ENACT will allow a wider and more effective use of data processed with in the continuum computing. It will enable real-time decision-making in applications such as manufacturing, media, telecommunication, and transportation and many other relevant sectors. By processing data at the edge, insights can be generated and acted upon immediately, leading to improved operational efficiency and reduced downtime. ENACT targets at increased and efficient data sharing thanks to business models and technologies that put data owner at the center, promote trust over data control and create wealth and adding value to new innovative connected services and products. The optimization in runtime qualities and the more effective and efficient use of resources, applications, services and data from IoT/ edge, through the ENACT technologies, e.g. AI ENACT orchestrator, APM based apps, etc., will allow a set of new applications with profound societal and QoL impact, such the use cases foreseen in the course of the project, (i.e. the enhanced end-to-end communication and hyper-personalized media content, the cloud-edge deployments in the mobility domain, etc.), thus maximizing both social and economic benefits from data. Furthermore, ENACT will foster and enhance the engagement of SMEs in the European industrial landscape, to promote innovation activities across the EU economy, while at the same time ensuring growth and adoption of AI and advanced solutions by stakeholders.

C. Reinforced EU ability to manage urgent societal challenges

ENACT fully embraces the EU Green Deal strategy towards climate net neutrality (especially CO2 footprint minimization), also aligning with several sustainable development goals of the United Nations, ranging from Affordable and Clean Energy and Climate Action to Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure. To this end, the target is to design energy aware data infrastructures that will avoid the explosion of ICT footprint and provide deeper understanding of the potential of decentralized intelligence to support green digital solutions by exploiting ML capabilities to process data from smart connected objects and decide the corrective actions, thus enabling efficient energy management. The developed criteria for the non-functional requirements' optimization will be integrated in the orchestrator and scheduler, and in combination with the computation closer to edge, will result in reduced energy consumption. Additionally, the quantified metrics and the visualization of all

¹⁷ <https://www.delltechnologies.com/asset/en-hk/products/dell-technologies-cloud/industry-market/the-edge-to-cloud-continuum.pdf>

¹⁸ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/edge-computing-market>

¹⁹ <https://mixed-news.com/en/meta-tests-5g-cloud-streaming-with-verizon/>

²⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-alliance>

energy/resource related parameters, will reinforce the users' ability to better understand and execute decisions.

D. Globally attractive, secure and dynamic data-agile economy, by developing and enabling the uptake of the next-generation computing and data technologies and infrastructures enabling the EU single market for data

In the long run, ENACT outcomes can enable a market shift from the widespread use of cloud-edge continuum market models that are currently dominated by non-EU entities, to a future strategy for European SMEs, providing a computing continuum with strong capabilities throughout the layers of it (infrastructure, data and computation). The uptake of ENACT system will contribute to a globally attractive, secure and dynamic data-agile economy, through its enabling technologies, (namely the Cognitive cloud fabric, the APM and the ENACT orchestrator), which will allow new ENACT living applications and services to be developed having AI-enabled cognition in the compute continuum. The provision of distributed data spaces' architecture will allow Europe to unhook itself from the non-EU current dependency. Furthermore, the employment of ENACT will enable data exploitation within the EU borders, which will improve the European economic indicators, while at the same time will ensure data privacy and sovereignty. Noteworthy, ENACT also offers excellence in the security and privacy management of AI enabled frameworks, contributing to trust building between different systems, enabling European industry to reinforce and regain leadership across the digital supply chain by supporting early discovery and uptake of new technologies.

In order to achieve the expected impact, the introduced ENACT framework has to address a series of concerns and risks that has been identified. Technological risks such as complex concept, lack of interoperability between the various components, difficulties in algorithmic design for orchestration, security issues across CCC etc. have to be addressed. Moreover, user related risks like the sharing of sensitive data, limited acceptance of the solution etc., low interpretability and understanding of solutions and AI decisions etc. have also been concerned.

To address the various technological level concerns, ENACT will continuously monitor the current state-of-the-art and setup a modular architecture based on well-known standards. Standards and widely used protocols, data models and technologies will be used to ensure interoperability of the ENACT CCC. ZTP and Next-Gen SDN will be applied to further support security and monitoring in CCC. Best practices during technical management and development (Scrum, Agile programming etc.) will be adopted as well. Regarding user related risks, FAIR principles²¹ will be followed related to data management and Data Spaces technologies to ensure data sovereignty and security. Explainable AI approaches will be used to further promote trustworthy and interpretable AI to bring human in the loop. Continuous workshops with end-users will be held to ensure application and acceptance of the ENACT outcomes and to meet the expected impact of the project.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a novel solution to help realise a Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) that can address the needs for optimal (edge and Cloud) resource management and

dynamic scaling, elasticity, and portability of hyper-distributed data-intensive applications.

At infrastructure level, the proposed ENACT solution brings visibility to distributed edge and Cloud resources by developing Dynamic Graph Models capable of capturing and visualising the real-time and historic status information, connectivity types, dependencies, energy consumption etc. from diverse edge and Cloud resources. The graph models are used by AI (Graph Neural Networks - GNN) models and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) agents to suggest the optimal deployment configurations for hyper distributed applications considering their specific needs. The AI (GNN and DRL) models are packaged as an intelligent decision-making engine that can replace the scheduling component of open-source solutions such as KubeEdge. This will enable real-time and predictive management of distributed infrastructure and applications. To take full advantage of the potential (compute, storage, energy efficiency etc.) opportunities in the CCC, ENACT also proposes an innovative Application Programming Model (APM). The APM will provide an innovative architecture, together with software libraries and developer resource to support the development of hyper-distributed and platform agnostic applications, capable of self-determining their optimal deployment and optimal execution configurations while taking advantage of diverse resources in the CCC. The APM can be realised through a SDK. Moreover, services for automatic (zero-touch provisioning-based) resource configuration and (telemetry) data collections are proposed as part of the overall ENACT solution to aid the design and update of dynamic graph models.

The proposed solution is currently being developed in the EC funded ENACT project. Once developed, the technological solutions and design guidelines will be tested and validated in 3 real-world scenarios. The findings of the testing and validation activity will be subsequently published in peer-reviewed conferences and journals. Further information about the ENACT project and its latest achievements can be found at: <https://enact-horizon.eu/>

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